

TIME MANAGEMENT: A WAY TO SUCCESS

Ms. Amritpal Kaur

Assistant Professor,

Institute of Educational Technology and Vocational Education,

Panjab University, Chandigarh

Abstract

Man is the most adaptive creature on the planet because of the evolution of the human brain, especially the part called the neo-cortex. This adaptability is largely due to the changes and stressors that we have faced and mastered. Therefore, we, unlike other animals, can live in any climate or ecosystem, at various altitudes, and avoid the danger of predators. Moreover, most recently, we have learned to live in the air, under the sea, and even in space, where no living creatures that we know of have ever survived. So then, what is so about Good Time Management? Time management is the act or process of planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities, especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency or productivity.

A time management system is a designed combination of processes, tools, techniques, and methods. Time management is usually a necessity in any project development as it determines the project completion time and scope. Time Management is the process of organizing and planning how much time we spend on specific activities. Time Management is managing your own time more efficiency, and save yourself time in the future.

Introduction

Time management is the act or process of planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities, especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency or productivity. It is a meta-activity with the goal to maximize the overall benefit of a set of other activities within the boundary condition of a limited amount of time. Time management may be aided by a range of skills, tools, and techniques used to manage time when accomplishing specific tasks, projects, and goals complying with a due date. Initially, time management referred to just business or work activities, but eventually the term broadened to include personal activities as well. A time management system is a designed combination of processes, tools, techniques, and methods. Time management is usually a necessity in any project development as it determines the project completion time and scope.

Man is the most adaptive creature on the planet because of the evolution of the human brain, especially the part called the neo-cortex. This adaptability is largely due to the changes and stressors that we have faced and mastered. But Good time management is essential to our success. Using an effective time planner and master list we can achieve any goal you set your mind to. Some time management tools and techniques that we should practice for maximum productivity and good personal organization. Each of them takes a little time to learn and master, but pays you back in greater efficiency and effectiveness for the rest of your life. Time Management is managing your own time more efficiency, and save yourself time in the future.

Time Management

“Time management” refers to the way that you organize and plan how long you spend on specific activities.

It may seem counter-intuitive to dedicate precious time to learning about time management, instead of using it to get on with your work, but the benefits are enormous:

- Greater productivity and efficiency.
- A better professional reputation.
- Less stress.
- Increased opportunities for advancement.
- Greater opportunities to achieve important life and career goals.

Time Management include the following:

- Creating an environment conducive to effectiveness
- Setting of priorities
- Carrying out activity around those priorities
- The related process of reduction of time spent on non-priorities
- Incentives to modify behaviour to ensure compliance with time-related deadlines.

Most of us are familiar with the famous proverb, “Time and tide wait for no one” which us true. The reason is that if you lose a minute, you are not going to be able to retrieve it again. There are days when you have worked continuously from morning till evening, yet could not complete your work. Have you wondered why this happens? It is because you

have not prioritise your task and managed manner. Remember that one that most important commodities that can never be bought at the supermarket is “Time.”

Why Time Management?

Time is limited scarce. You must be aware that each individual has the same number of hours, yet you would notice some people complaining about the lack of time. You are bound to get out of focus when there is so little time and you have so much to do. Hence, for efficient time management, it is import to set priorities and meet deadlines. When you start prioritising things, you would notice that there is enough time for all the crucial activities in life. Neither the rich nor the poor can store time. The quota of 24 hours is given to all men. The main difference between fame and failure lies in how one uses their time skilfully. Hence, time management is all about wise usage of what time is available.

Time management helps you in organising yourself. If you could allot a certain amount of time for each work or activity, you would have no worries about achieving your target. Managing time is all about getting organised. Remember that time is needed for each and every activity that you undertake. You should know how to divide your working hours among the various activities of the day. This would ensure that a task is completed and the time used is accounted for.

Students and Time Management

Time is an important for a student. A student does a lot of activities in his daily routine, out of which some (study) are related to his career, some (having food) are essential for his life and some (games etc) are for entertainment or physical fitness. Still some activities have no use and just waste time. Similarly if the activities for entertainment exceeds than enough it wastes the time of a student like using internet (chatting and emails for recreation) for hours, playing games for hours, watching movies for hours or listening to music for hours. Such activities are called “distracters” which distract one from one’s real purpose. Games and physical exercise are important for a student because it refreshes his mind and it keeps him physically and mentally fit but games’ time should not exceeded than sufficient that it may waste your time.

Time management is not only to allocate time against different subjects but also to identify right time for each such subject, how much time should be given to different subject

and to identify the distracters which become causes of wastage of time. If anyone spoils his/her time. Time will ruin his/her.

Time Management in Workplace

Managing your time at the workplace is of great importance. It would relieve you of the stress and strain of the working environment. Time management is a skill that could be acquired by participating it religiously. Lessening your stress at the workplace by practicing this skill is very important. Poor management of time leads to backlogs, and the piled up work leads to unnecessary stress. Time management skills help in increasing the efficiency at workplace. If we are able to finish our targets by managing proper time well no doubt it will lead us to success.

How to Manage Time

1. Keep track

Keeping a time log is a helpful way to determine how you are using your time. Start by recording what you are doing for 15-minute intervals for a week or two. Evaluate the results. Ask if you did everything that was needed; determine which tasks require the most time; determine the time of day when you are most productive; and analyze where most of your time is devoted – job, family, personal, recreation, etc. Identifying your most time-consuming tasks and determining whether you are investing your time in the most important activities can help you to determine a course of action. In addition, having a good sense of the amount of time required for routine tasks can help you be more realistic in planning and estimating how much time is available for other activities.

2. Set Priorities

Managing your time effectively requires a distinction between what is *important* and what is *urgent* (MacKenzie, 1990). Experts agree that the most important tasks usually aren't the most urgent tasks. However, we tend to let the urgent dominate our lives.

3. Use a Planning Tool

The key is to find one planning tool that works for you and use that tool consistently. Some reminders when using a planning tool are:

- Always record your information on the tool itself. Jotting notes elsewhere that have to be transferred later is inefficient.

- Review your planning tool daily.
- Carry your planning tool with you.
- Remember to keep a list of your priorities in your planning tool and refer to it often.
- Synchronize electronic planners with your computer and recharge the batteries in your planner on a regular basis.
- Keep a back-up system.

4. Proper Organisation

Most people find that disorganization results in poor time management. Professional organizers recommend that you first get rid of the clutter. With the clutter gone, the next step is to implement a system that allows you to handle information (e.g., tasks, papers, e-mail, etc.) less, only once, when possible.

5. Schedule Your Time Appropriately

Good scheduling requires that you know yourself. Using your time log, you should have determined those times during the day when you are most productive and alert. Plan your most challenging tasks for when you have the most energy. Block out time for your high priority activities first and protect that time from interruptions.

6. Stop Procrastinating

You may be putting off tasks for a variety of reasons. Perhaps the task seems overwhelming or unpleasant. Try breaking down the task into smaller segments that require less time commitment and result in specific, realistic deadlines. If you're having trouble getting started, you may need to complete a preparatory task such as collecting materials or organizing your notes. Also, try building in a reward system as you complete each small segment of the task.

7. Avoid Multi-tasking

Recent psychological studies have shown that multi-tasking does not actually save time. In fact, the opposite is often true. You lose time when switching from one task to another, resulting in a loss of productivity (Rubinsteim, Meyer, and Evans, 2001). Routine multi-tasking may lead to difficulty in concentrating and maintaining focus when needed.

8. Stay Healthy

Poor time management can result in fatigue, moodiness, and more frequent illness. To reduce stress, you should reward yourself for a time management success. The care and

attention you give yourself is an important investment of time. Scheduling time to relax, or do nothing, can help you rejuvenate both physically and mentally, enabling you to accomplish tasks more quickly and easily. Take time to recognize that you have accomplished a major task or challenge before moving on to the next activity.

In Nut shell

Time management is essential in every field of life because time is the precious recourse one has to accomplish a task. A very single moment which passed once will never come back to be availed. Time management helps you do your task in time and utilize your time more productively. It helps you to identify the useless activities which can be avoided and time can be saved. It helps you give proper time to a task and perform the task more efficiently. Time Management is managing your own time more efficiency, and save yourself time in the future. If we will not use time in a better way, we will not success in life. Time is very important in life, without managing the time it will be lead to failure in life.

References

- MacKenzie, A. (1990). *The Time Trap* (3rd ed.). New York: American Management Association.
- Rubinstein, J., Meyer, D. & Evans, J. (2001). Executive control of cognitive processes in task switching. *Journal of Experimental Psychology – Human Perception and Performance*, 27(4), 763-797.
- Time Management Strategies retrieved from <http://www.buzzle.com/articles/time-management-strategies.html>
- Time Management Tools and Techniques retrieved from <http://www.briantracy.com/blog/time-management/time-management-tools-and-techniques-time-planner-master-list/>
- What is Time Management? retrieved from http://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newHTE_00.htm

Copyrights @ Ms. Amritpal Kaur. This is an open access reviewed article distributed under the creative common attribution license which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provide the original work is cited.